

Extended analysis of related work on modeling theory: RCMs of Model, Metamodel and Modeling language

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1. Related work

Compiling a related work section about modeling is a challenging task. The literature on modeling is very extensive and has evolved over time. Perspectives vary greatly and thus far researchers have not reached a consensus regarding the terminology [1], [2]. Evidence of this can be found in our previous article [3], wherein an in-depth review of 200 references about modeling was conducted.

Before proceeding, a couple of issues about this study should be noted. Firstly, it is not our intention to cover all types of modeling. Formal approaches to modeling, for example, are not addressed herein. Moreover, for the sake of brevity, an innovative tool of our creation called RCM (*Reference-enriched Concept Maps*) [4] is employed to visually summarize the definitions of many authors in the literature on a particular topic. This topic to which a RCM refers is called *main concept*. A RCM provides the reader with the key concepts within those definitions, their relationships and, most notably, the references in which they appear, thus allowing the reader to reconstruct the original definitions collected in a RCM. RCM classifies the concepts in layers (primary, secondary, etc.), helping to highlight the relative importance of the concepts from the point of view of the RCM author. You can read a complete description of RCM in [4].

Next, we use RCMs to study three principal modeling concepts: model, metamodel and modeling language.

1.1 Concept of model

Many authors have already defined model, each contributing parts of the whole truth. The next figure, labeled as RCM 1, summarizes how researchers understand and define model. In order to obtain this RCM, twenty-six definitions from twenty references were used (note the summarizing capacity of RCM). Three layers of concepts were considered (ten primary, seven secondary and six tertiary), which are represented by different colors (primary in dark gray, secondary in light gray, tertiary in white). The RCM labels can be employed to reconstruct each of the definitions, following the label on each path. For example, following the path labeled with 13 the Bézivin's view of model arises: 'Model is a simplification of a system, is for a goal, and allows to answer questions about a system'.

Reading the RCM reveals, among other things, that many authors consider a model to be a *representation* or *description* either of a *system* (Bézivin, Ober, Kleppe...), or of a mental construction of a domain (Sánchez), or of a software abstraction (Jackson), or of reality (Pidd). Other authors (Aßmann, OMG) also define model as a specification of a system; and still others as a simplification or abstraction either of a system (Kühne, OMG, Bézivin), or of an original (Stachowiak), or of reality (Mellor). However Seidewitz and Gonzalez-Perez see model as a statement, or a set of statements, about a system. RCM 1 also illustrates the relationship between model and language, such as when Gonzalez-Perez, Seidewitz or Kühne, among others, claim that models are expressed in a *modeling language*. And finally, the *purpose* of modeling is profusely referred to when model is defined. Additionally, other authors underline that a model can be used in place of the modeled system, for example to make *predictions* or to answer *questions* about the *reality* (Mellor) or the *system* (Ober, Kühne ...).

The RCM technique offers much more than a mere summarized compilation of different opinions about a certain concept. It is actually suited for analyzing these differences. For this purpose, RCM defines a total of

concept scattering; the value of this metric is inversely proportional to the degree of consensus regarding the importance of a concept appearing in the collected definitions. For example, a concept scattering of 0% at the primary layer would indicate that all definitions coincide in choosing a certain concept as the principal meaning of the main concept of the RCM. The RCM of model has a concept scattering of 40% at the primary layer, 20% at secondary and 16% at the tertiary. Similarly, the *semantic scattering* can be assessed, calculated over semantic fields, i.e. groups of concepts with a similar meaning for the RCM creator. To determine this similarity, the RCM creator can take the literature into account (e.g. the literature usually classifies models as descriptive or prescriptive; therefore, in our opinion, representation and description are similar terms, as they both refer to descriptive models). In this case, we found that the semantic scattering differs from concept scattering only at the primary layer (28% vs. 40%). This indicates that the differences appear mainly on the primary layer, where some authors utilized similar concepts (e.g., representation–description or specification–abstraction), while also introducing nuances that prevented them from reaching a consensus on the primary concept of the model meaning. Another interesting metric is the *definition essentiality* (for the details of the calculation formula see [4]), which is calculated according to an aggregation of the density of references of each of the concepts comprising each definition in a certain RCM. For the RCM of model, this metric reveals that there are three essential definitions (with an essentiality factor greater than 40%): ‘model is a description of a system’, ‘model is a specification of a system’ and ‘model is an abstraction of a system’.

1.2 Concept of metamodel

The RCM of metamodel (RCM 2) was based on seventeen definitions from fourteen references. Twelve concepts, including seven primary and five secondary, were identified. The lack of agreement regarding the meaning of metamodel is evident when calculating the concept scattering: 37.5% in the primary layer and 25% in the secondary layer. The most interesting conclusions regarding the RCM of metamodel become evident when it is compared with the RCM of model. We can see that most of its primary concepts are also primary concepts in the RCM of model (specification, abstraction, description or model itself), and the rest are related to language and grammar. Thus, we can conclude that the definitions of metamodel are polarized around two points of view: those who believe that metamodel is a particular case of model (Bézivin, Kühne, Seidewitz, OMG...), and those who identify it with grammar or language (Ober, Joyce, OMG...). However both positions are related, since part of the definitions using concepts of the former, go on to use secondary concepts of the latter: specification of abstract syntax (Gonzalez-Perez); model defining a language (OMG); or specification, or model, of a modeling language (Aßmann, Seidewitz, Favre...). This RCM demonstrates that many authors relate metamodel to modeling language.

1.3 Concept of modeling language

The RCM of modeling language (RCM 3) comprises eight definitions from eight references. Twelve concepts were considered: five primary, six secondary, one tertiary. Clearly, most definitions (Overbeek, Seidewitz, Harel...) include language as a primary concept. The concept scattering is higher at the secondary layer (62.5% vs. 50% in the primary), where, as expected, model is the most popular concept (Overbeek, Bauer, Favre). Consistent with our above observations, one of the definitions (Boronat) uses metamodel as a secondary concept. And lastly, note that the model-system-language triangle appears in this RCM in two references (Seidewitz, Harel).

These RCM, in addition to revealing the key terms of modeling, demonstrate how often the concepts of model, language and system appear together in the literature. The RCMs also draw attention to the lack of consensus on the meaning of basic modeling terms, at least regarding theories of object-oriented modeling – one of the most widely used forms of modeling.

Now that the foremost modeling concepts have been reviewed, our focus turns to an overview of the bibliography of the principal contributions to the theory of modeling in general. Kühne [5], in collaboration with other authors such as Atkinson [6] has been one of the most prolific authors in this field. His principal contributions have been the distinction between type and token models, linguistic and ontological instantiation, and between classification and inheritance. Gonzalez-Perez and Henderson-Sellers [7], [8] have also made various contributions regarding the classification of models according to mappings (isotypical, prototypical, metatypical) powertypes and clabjects. Bézivin has also published many articles (e.g., [9], [10]) pertinent to

[1] J. Bézivin, "On the unification power of models," *Software and Systems Modeling*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 171–188, May 2005.

[2] OMG, "MetaObject Facility (MOF) 2.0 Core specification." Jan-2006.

[3] T. Kühne, "Matters of (Meta-) Modeling," *Software and Systems Modeling*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 395–401, Dec. 2006.

[4] E. Seidewitz, "What Models Mean," *IEEE Software*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 26–32, Sep. 2003.

[5] U. AlBmann, S. Zschaler, and G. Wagner, "Ontologies, Meta-models, and the Model-Driven Paradigm," *Ontologies for Software Engineering and Software Technology*, pp. 249–273, 2006.

[6] C. Gonzalez-Perez and B. Henderson-Sellers, "Modelling software development methodologies: A conceptual foundation," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 80, no. 11, pp. 1778–1796, Nov. 2007.

[7] I. Kurtev, "Metamodels: Definitions of Structures or Ontological Commitments," in *Workshop on TOWERS of models. Collocated with TOOLS Europe 2007*, 2007, vol. 2007.

[8] I. Ober and A. Prinz, "What do we need metamodels for?," in *4th Nordic Workshop on UML and Software Modelling*, 2006, pp. 8–28.

[9] OMG, "MetaObject Facility (MOF) 1.4." Apr-2002.

[10] J.-M. Favre, "Foundations of meta-pyramids: Languages vs. metamodels Episode II: Story of thotus the baboon," *Language Engineering for Model-Driven Software Development*, vol. 4101, 2005.

[11] OMG, "MDA Guide Version 1.0.1." 12-Jun-2003.

[12] A. Pierantonio and S. Zacchiroli, "Metamodel for Describing System Structure and State," 2009. [Online]. Available: <http://upsilon.cc/~zack/research/publications/mancoosi-d2.1.pdf>.

[13] S. J. Mellor, K. Scott, A. Uhl, D. Weise, and R. M. Soley, *MDA distilled: principles of model-driven architecture*, vol. 88. New York: Addison-Wesley, 2004.

[14] G. H. Joyce, *Principles of logic*. London: Longmans, Green and Co., 1916.

RCM 2 RCM of metamodel

modeling theory focused on OMG. He distinguishes between the relationships instance-of and conforms-to. And, in his classic article [9] he compares OO with modeling to affirm that they are both a model. In a similar vein, he has also developed tools based on Eclipse [11] by working with metamodels based on OMG, though they are more simple. Seidewitz [12] proposes an approach that has greatly influenced modeling theory. The distinction he draws between the formal view (model theory) and the non-formal (modeling theory) should be underscored. By starting with a mathematically oriented definition, he addresses the principal modeling issues: descriptive vs. prescriptive, metamodel, modeling language, minimal model, relating them to the OMG approach. Stachowiak y Ludewig [13], [14] have also been of great influence in the field as they outlined the three primary characteristics of models: reduction, mapping, pragmatic. Favre [15], [16] focuses his discussion on megamodels (models of MDE) and gives equal attention to the central issues of model, metamodel, and modeling language by defining the primary relationships among these concepts. Most notable is his statement regarding the key question of distinguishing between descriptive and prescriptive models: 'who, of the model

[1] I. J. F. Overbeek, "Meta Object Facility (MOF) investigation of the state of the art," University of Twente, 2006.

[2] E. Seidewitz, "What Models Mean," *IEEE Software*, vol. 20, no. 5, pp. 26–32, Sep. 2003.

[3] S. Cook, "Domain-Specific Modeling and Model Driven Architecture," *MDA Journal*, January, pp. 2–10, 2004.

[4] B. Bauer and J. Odell, "UML 2.0 and agents: how to build agent-based systems with the new UML standard," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 141–157, Mar. 2005.

[5] C. Gonzalez-Perez and B. Henderson-Sellers, "Modelling software development methodologies: A conceptual foundation," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 80, no. 11, pp. 1778–1796, Nov. 2007.

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RCM 3 RCM of modeling language

or the system, have the truth' [16]. Rensink [17] offers a different approach that defines model as a 'subject' with an associated 'member-of' function. He also formally defines metamodel and modeling language, and compares models with ontologies and theorizes on the relationships of similarity (description, representation, instance-of, is-a, subset). Muller et al. [2] focus on the intention of a model and then goes on to define a formal notation to demonstrate the relationships between the purpose of a model and the purpose of the modeled object.

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